

IMPLEMENTING A BRAIN POWER CURRICULUM TO ENHANCE META- LEARNING AND COGNITIVE SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article proposes the implementation of an innovative educational program entitled Brain Power at an International School in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. The program is designed to enhance students' cognitive abilities through the development of meta-learning skills, memory improvement, accelerated learning techniques, and increased reading speed. Drawing on the educational philosophies of Jim Kwik, Anthony Robbins, and Tom Bilyeu, the curriculum aims to help learners unlock their intellectual potential and develop effective lifelong learning strategies. The proposal targets students in Grades 5–10, with an initial pilot study involving Grade 10 learners. The program integrates modern learning methodologies, mindset development, and practical cognitive exercises to address common challenges faced by adolescents, including low self-esteem, academic difficulties, and lack of motivation. Through a structured implementation process and continuous evaluation, the Brain Power curriculum seeks to improve students' academic performance, personal growth, and readiness for future educational and professional success.

Keywords: Brain Power, Meta-learning, Cognitive Development, Accelerated Learning, Memory Enhancement, Reading Speed, Mindset Transformation, Secondary Education, Student Achievement, Educational Innovation.

ВНЕДРЕНИЕ УЧЕБНОЙ ПРОГРАММЫ «BRAIN POWER» ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ МЕТАОБУЧЕНИЯ И КОГНИТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ У УЧАЩИХСЯ СРЕДНЕЙ ШКОЛЫ

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Аннотация: В данной статье предлагается внедрение инновационной образовательной программы под названием «Brain Power» в международной школе города Ташкента, Узбекистан. Программа направлена на развитие когнитивных способностей учащихся посредством формирования навыков метаобучения, улучшения памяти, освоения методов ускоренного обучения и повышения скорости чтения. Основанная на образовательных концепциях Джима Квика, Энтони Роббинса и Тома Билью, программа ставит своей целью раскрытие интеллектуального потенциала обучающихся и формирование эффективных стратегий обучения на протяжении всей жизни. Проект ориентирован на учащихся 5–10 классов, при этом первоначальное пилотное исследование предполагается провести среди учеников 10 класса. Программа объединяет современные образовательные методики, развитие мышления и

практические когнитивные упражнения для решения распространённых проблем подростков, включая низкую самооценку, трудности в обучении и недостаток мотивации. Благодаря поэтапному внедрению и систематической оценке результатов программа «Brain Power» направлена на повышение академической успеваемости учащихся, их личностное развитие и подготовку к дальнейшему образовательному и профессиональному успеху.

Ключевые слова: Brain Power, метаобучение, когнитивное развитие, ускоренное обучение, улучшение памяти, скорость чтения, трансформация мышления, среднее образование, успеваемость учащихся, образовательные инновации.

INTRODUCTION

“You have the power and the responsibility inside” Jim Kwik

Power is considered to be very strong emotional word. Human beings’ reactions and responses to this word are often desperate. Some people assume that this word has a negative connotation. Some people run after it by not understanding true meaning of this word since they do think in terms of conquering others. In fact, ultimate power is a distinct skill and ability to manufacture desirable results and make the things to work for us and not against us. Real power is the ability to alter our life and shape our values and perceptions (Robbins, 2018).

This proposal is considered to be a new science in teaching process since it might help to change the mindset of the learners and unleash their potential. Additionally, it assists learners in accelerating their brain power. The name of the course is “Brain Power”. This course is based on the program of outstanding memory booster Jim Kwik, Neuro-Linguistics programming and psychological book “Unlimited power” by Anthony Robbins was taken as a basement. In addition, the Impact Theory program by Tom Bilyeu was also selected as an inspirational part of this proposal. This course is designed to be implemented as a subject into the program of desperate educational settings such as tertiary education, international schools, private schools and governmental schools. However, the first experiment of implementation of this distinct program will occur in an International school which is situated in Tashkent. There are three main campuses at school: International Baccalaureate (IB), Russian school and Kindergarten. The number of the students are approximately seven hundred. The International Baccalaureate campus trains students in IB program and all the subjects are taught in English language. In current time, primary schoolchildren study in the IB program. It has been already planned to open classes to high school children from the new school year. School experiments diverse methods and strategies in order to foster the education system.

Researcher decided to implement this program from the fifth till tenth grades due to many reasons. According to many researches, teenagers suffer from many social problems such as depression, anxiety, academic problems, low self-esteem, bullying, social media addiction and many others (Morin, 2109). For this reason, this course might be helpful for them in finding their own way in life by realizing their potential.

The students are mostly bilingual. All of them prefer Russian or English language. Each class does have learners from desperate nations such as Korean, Tatar, Russian, Uzbek, Kazakh, Kirgiz and Chinese. Most of the students were born in the United States of America and grew up there until their puberty. These pupils are considered to be native speakers of English language even though they are from Uzbek nationalities. They always prefer to speak only English language.

MAIN BODY

The main target of the proposal is to change the mindset of the learners which is considered to be contributing factor in their future life.

The ultimate objectives that have to be accomplished at the end of the course are the following:

- To improve meta learning
- To accelerate learning
- To increase reading speed
- To improve memory

Researcher decided to put forward meta-learning as the ultimate objective of the course. The field of meta-learning has an impact on today’s education system and has seen a continuous growth. Meta-learning is the science where learners learn how to learn, how to be creative, how to be a problem solver and remember more information (Weng, 2018).

Inventory: The school is equipped with necessary technological equipment such as smartboards, laptops and speakers. Instructors are always provided with inevitable stationary. Financial side of the program is covered by the school.

The outlined below equipment is necessary for the program:

Equipment	Availability	Total amount	Price of per item	Total price
Smartboard	+	1	-	-
Speaker	+	1	-	-
Laptop	+	1	-	-
I pad	+	15	-	-
“Unlimited Power” book by Anthony Robbins	-	200	18 \$	3600\$

Recommendations: The current program has not been implemented into the school system of Uzbekistan yet. The proposal was inspired and written due to other programs such as “Super Brain Quest” by Jim Kwik and “Impact theory” program by Tom Bilyeu. The program “Brain Quest” is considered to be an accelerated learning curriculum which is designed to activate brain’s limitless potential and helps to unlock the full power of the mind. This program helps millions of people to experience life-changing evaluations in their career and personal growth (Kwik learning, n.d). This program mainly utilizes meta-learning. Meta-learning is known as learning how to learn. This quick program with the help of cutting-edge techniques, different exercises and mind shifts can completely transform how people absorb, process and utilize the information (Weng, 2018). Another program is “Impact theory” which was developed by Tom Bilyeu. Tom created “Impact Theory” in order to help millions of people to achieve excellence, manifest right belief systems and enhance their life skills which are considered to be essential in the 21st century. This program is a weekly interview show with the highest achievers. These people share their challenging situations in the past and tell their secrets which led them eventually to success. Impact theory program consists of 25 belief system principles which were developed by Tom Bilyeu (Impact theory, n.d).

Timeline: The program consists of the following steps:

Phase 1

The first step includes preparation for the course and it is planning to be held in summer 2026. The presentation of the program will take place at school among school managing team, local and native English teachers and experts. Then desperate workshops will be held among teachers and

experts in terms of lesson plans and authentic materials. After selecting all the resources thoroughly, lesson plans for six months will be written among English teachers. All the responsibilities will be divided among experts and teachers. Then classroom and necessary equipment for the course will be arranged and organized accordingly.

Phase 2

This step includes selecting experimental group for the pilot study. For the experiment will be selected grade 10 who are sixteen years old. The class consists of ten students.

Phase 3

The pilot study lasts for six months. After this period, the gained results will be analyzed thoroughly. The weaknesses of the program will be identified and eliminated.

Phase 4

This phase consists of the real implementation of the program into the school system as a subject among 5th and 10th grade pupils.

Phase 5

After the implementation, the program lasts till the end of the school year. At the end of the school year, this program might demonstrate its exceptional results. The outstanding results can be seen from the academic performance of the learners in other subjects.

ACTORS

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

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